

OPERATIONS ON P-ORDER AND R-ORDER OF EXTERNAL CUBIC SOFT MATRICES

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce the notion of P-order (R-order) of external cubic soft matrices. Further, we develop union and intersection of P-order (R-order) of external cubic soft matrices and their related properties have been investigated.

Key Words: Cubic Soft Sets, Cubic Soft Matrices, P-Order External Cubic Soft Matrices & R-Order External Cubic Soft Matrices.

1. Introduction:

Fuzzy set theory was proposed by Lotfi A. Zadeh [12] and it has extensive applications in various fields. In 1999, Molodstov[8] introduced the novel concept of soft sets and established the fundamental results of the new theory. In 2003, Maji *et al.*[6] studied some properties of soft sets. Pei and Miao [10] and Chen [1] *et al.*, improved the work of Maji *et al.* [5, 6]. In [3], Jun *et al.*, introduced a new notion of cubic set which is a combination of fuzzy set and interval-valued fuzzy set and also investigated several properties of cubic sets.

Muhiuddin and Al-roqi [9], introduced the concepts of internal, external cubic soft sets, P-cubic (R-cubic) soft subsets, R-union(R-intersection, P-union and P-intersection) of cubic soft sets and the complement of a cubic soft sets. They also investigated several related properties and applied the notion of cubic soft sets to BCK/BCI-algebras.

Fuzzy matrix was introduced by Thomason [11] and the concept of uncertainty was discussed by using fuzzy matrices. Different concepts and ideas of fuzzy matrices have been given earlier mainly by Kim, Meenakshi and Thomson [4, 7, 11]. Fuzzy matrix plays a vital role in fuzzy modeling, fuzzy diagnosis and fuzzy controls. It also has applications in fields like psychology, medicine, economics and sociology.

In the early investigation, Chinnadurai and Barkavi introduced a new concepts of cubic soft matrix, internal cubic soft matrix, external cubic soft matrix and discussed various result in[2].

In this paper, the new definition of P-order external cubic soft matrices and R-order external cubic soft matrices have been introduced, along with some algebraic properties are discussed with suitable illustrations.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section we recall some basic definitions and results which will be needed in the sequel.

Definition 2.1 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set over U is defined to be a pair (Φ, A) where Φ is a mapping from A to $P(U)$ and $A \subseteq E$. Then the pair (Φ, A) can be represented as, $(\Phi, A) = \{\Phi(e)/e \in A\}$ where $\Phi(e) = \{u, \tilde{A}_e(u), \lambda_e(u)\}/u \in U, e \in A\}$ is a cubic soft set in which $\tilde{A}_e(u)$ is the interval valued fuzzy set and $\lambda_e(u)$ is a fuzzy set.

Definition 2.2 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is said to be an internal cubic soft set if $A_e^-(u) \leq \lambda_e(u) \leq A_e^+(u)$ for all $e \in A$ and for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.3 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is said to be an external cubic soft set if $\lambda_e(u) \notin (A_e^-(u), A_e^+(u))$ for all $e \in A$ and for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.4 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. For any subsets A and B of E , (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) be cubic soft sets over U .

1. The R-union of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cup B$ and

$$H(e) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cup_R \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$ and it is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cup_R (\Gamma, B)$.

2. The R-intersection of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cap B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cap_R \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$ and it is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cap_R (\Gamma, B)$.

Definition 2.5 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. For any subsets A and B of E , (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) be cubic soft sets over U .

1. The P-union of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cup B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cup_P \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cup_P (\Gamma, B)$.

2. The P-intersection of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cap B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cap_P \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cap_P (\Gamma, B)$.

Definition 2.6 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. The complement of a cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is denoted by $(\Phi, A)^c$ and defined by

$$(\Phi, A)^c = (\Phi^c, -A) \text{ where } \Phi^c : -A \rightarrow XP(U) \text{ and } (\Phi, A)^c = \{ \Phi^c(e) / e \in A \} \text{ where } \Phi^c(e) = \{ \langle u, \tilde{A}_e^c(u), \lambda_e^c(u) \rangle / u \in U, e \in A \}$$

Definition 2.7 [7] A matrix $A = [a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ is said to be fuzzy matrix if $a_{ij} \in [0, 1], 1 \leq i \leq m$ and $1 \leq j \leq n$.

Definition 2.8 [7] For any two fuzzy matrices $A = [a_{ij}], B = [b_{ij}]$ and a scalar $k \in F$. Then,

- (i) $A + B = [sup \{a_{ij}, b_{ij}\}] = \vee [a_{ij}, b_{ij}]$.
- (ii) $AB = [sup \{inf \{a_{ij}, b_{ij}\}\}] = \vee \{ \wedge [a_{ij}, b_{ij}] \}$.
- (iii) $kA = [inf \{k, a_{ij}\}] = \wedge [k, a_{ij}]$.

Definition 2.9 [2] Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ be an initial universal set and $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be a set of parameters. Let $A \subseteq E$. Then cubic soft set (Φ, A) can be expressed in matrix form as

$$A^c = [a_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

such that $A^c = [a_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{A}_{e_j}^a(u_i), \lambda_{e_j}^a(u_i) \rangle = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ which is called an $m \times n$ cubic soft matrix (shortly CS-matrix or CSM) of the cubic soft set (Φ, A) .

According to this definition, a cubic soft set (Φ, A) is uniquely characterized by matrix $[a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

Example 2.10 Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ is a set of cars and $A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is a set of parameters, which stands for mileage, engine and Prize respectively. Then cubic soft set is defined as

$$(\Phi, A) = \left\{ \begin{aligned} & [e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.5, 0.8] 0.6 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.1, 0.7] 0.5 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.6] 0.9 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.9] 0.4 \rangle)], \\ & [e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.2, 0.5] 0.3 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.3, 0.6] 0.7 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.7] 0.2 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.5] 0.1 \rangle)], \\ & [e_3, (u_1, \langle [0.1, 0.8] 0.4 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.6, 0.7] 0.9 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.9] 0.5 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.7] 0.4 \rangle)] \end{aligned} \right\}.$$

Then the CS-matrix A^c is written as,

$$A^c = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.5, 0.8] 0.6 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.5] 0.3 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.8] 0.4 \rangle \\ \langle [0.1, 0.7] 0.5 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.6] 0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.6, 0.7] 0.9 \rangle \\ \langle [0.2, 0.6] 0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.7] 0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.9] 0.5 \rangle \\ \langle [0.3, 0.9] 0.4 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.5] 0.1 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.7] 0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix}.$$

Definition 2.11 [2] Let $A^c = [a_{ij}] \in CSM_{m \times n}$. Then A^c is an external cubic soft matrix (ECSM), if $\lambda_{ij}^a \notin (\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+})$ for all i, j .

Definition 2.12 [2] Let $A^c = [a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$, $B^c = [b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ be the two cubic soft matrix of order $m \times n$. Then P-order matrix is denoted and defined as $[a_{ij}] \subseteq_P [b_{ij}]$, if $\tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

Definition 2.13 [2] Let $A^c = [a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$, $B^c = [b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ be the two cubic soft matrix of order $m \times n$. Then R-order matrix is denoted and defined as $[a_{ij}] \subseteq_R [b_{ij}]$, if $\tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

Definition 2.14 [2] Let $A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$, $B^c = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \in CSM_{m \times n}$. Then

1. P-union of A^c and B^c is denoted by $A^c \vee_P B^c$ and defined as $A^c \vee_P B^c = C^c$, if $C^c = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .
2. P-intersection of A^c and B^c is denoted by $A^c \wedge_P B^c$ and defined as $A^c \wedge_P B^c = C^c$, if $C^c = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .
3. R-union of A^c and B^c is denoted by $A^c \vee_R B^c$ and defined as $A^c \vee_R B^c = C^c$, if $C^c = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .
4. R-intersection of A^c and B^c is denoted by $A^c \wedge_R B^c$ and defined as $A^c \wedge_R B^c = C^c$, if $C^c = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .

3. P-order and R-order of External Cubic Soft Matrices.

In this section we define P-order and R-order of external cubic soft matrix and discussed some algebraic properties.

Definition 3.1 Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ and $B^c = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ be external cubic soft matrices, if $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j . Then it is defined as P-order external cubic soft matrices and it is denoted by $ECSM^P$.

Example 3.2 Let $U = \{u_1, u_2\}$ be the universal set and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ be the set of parameters. Let $A, B \subseteq E$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\Phi, A) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} & [e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.3, 0.5] 0.2 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.4, 0.6] 0.3 \rangle)], \\ & [e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.1, 0.5] 0.7 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.4, 0.6] 0.2 \rangle)] \end{aligned} \right\} \text{ and} \\ (\Phi, B) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} & [e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.4, 0.6] 0.9 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.7, 0.9] 1 \rangle)], \\ & [e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.2, 0.8] 0.85 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.7, 0.9] 0.4 \rangle)] \end{aligned} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then P-order external cubic soft matrices is defined as follows,

$$A^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.3, 0.5], 0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.5], 0.7 \rangle \\ \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.3 \rangle & \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \subseteq_P B^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.9 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.8], 0.85 \rangle \\ \langle [0.7, 0.9], 1 \rangle & \langle [0.7, 0.9], 0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

(i.e) $A^{\langle} \subseteq_P B^{\langle}$.

Definition 3.3 Let $A^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ and $B^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ be external cubic soft matrices, if $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \geq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j. Then it is defined as R-order external cubic soft matrices and it is denoted by $ECSM^R$.

Example 3.4 Let $U = \{u_1, u_2\}$ be the universal set and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ be the set of parameters. Let $A, B \subseteq E$. Then

$$(\Phi, A) = \{ [e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.2, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.8 \rangle)], [e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.1, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle)] \}$$

and

$$(\Phi, B) = \{ [e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.6, 0.9], 0.5 \rangle)], [e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.5, 0.8], 0.1 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.4, 0.7], 0.3 \rangle)] \}.$$

Then R-order external cubic soft matrices is defined as follows,

$$A^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.2, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle \\ \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.8 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.5, 0.8], 0.1 \rangle \\ \langle [0.6, 0.9], 0.5 \rangle & \langle [0.4, 0.7], 0.3 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

(i.e) $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle}$.

Definition 3.5 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle} \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$. Then

a) Union of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ is defined by $A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} = C^{\langle} = [c_{ij}]$,

where $C^{\langle} = \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle$ for all i, j.

b) Intersection of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ is defined by $A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} = C^{\langle} = [c_{ij}]$,

where $C^{\langle} = \langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle$ for all i, j.

Example 3.6 Consider Example 3.2. Then union and intersection of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ are given by,

$$a) A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.9 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.8], 0.85 \rangle \\ \langle [0.7, 0.9], 1 \rangle & \langle [0.7, 0.9], 0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

$$b) A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.3, 0.5], 0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.5], 0.7 \rangle \\ \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.3 \rangle & \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 3.7 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle} \in ECSM_{m \times n}^R$. Then

a) Union of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ is defined by $A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle} = C^{\langle} = [c_{ij}]$,

where $C^{\langle} = \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle$ for all i, j.

b) Intersection of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ is defined by $A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} = C^{\langle} = [c_{ij}]$,

where $C^{\langle} = \langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle$ for all i, j.

Example 3.8 Consider Example 3.4. Then union and intersection of $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}$ are given by,

$$a) A^c \vee_R B^c = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.5, 0.8], 0.1 \rangle \\ \langle [0.6, 0.9], 0.5 \rangle & \langle [0.4, 0.7], 0.3 \rangle \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$b) A^c \wedge_R B^c = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.2, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.6], 0.2 \rangle \\ \langle [0.4, 0.6], 0.8 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.4], 0.7 \rangle \end{bmatrix}.$$

Proposition 3.9 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$. Then

(i) $A^c \vee_P A^c = A^c$.

(ii) $A^c \vee_P B^c = B^c$.

(iii) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = A^c \vee_P (B^c \vee_P C^c) = C^c$.

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$.

Then (i) $A^c \vee_P A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_P A^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \lambda_{ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \vee_P A^c &= \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^c. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^c \vee_P B^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \vee_P B^c &= \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= B^c. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \vee_P C^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_P C^c &= \left(\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \right) \vee_P C^c \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_P C^c \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_P \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_P C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_p B^c) \vee_p C^c &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $A^c \vee_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) = C^c$.

Hence, $(A^c \vee_p B^c) \vee_p C^c = A^c \vee_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) = C^c$.

Proposition 3.10 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ECSM_{m \times n}^R$. Then

- (i) $A^c \vee_R A^c = A^c$.
- (ii) $A^c \vee_R B^c = B^c$.
- (iii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = A^c \vee_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = C^c$.

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ECSM_{m \times n}^R$.

Then (i) $A^c \vee_R A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_R A^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \lambda_{ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \vee_R A^c &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^c \vee_R B^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \vee_R B^c &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= B^c. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right) \vee_R C^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \left(\left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \vee_R C^c \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R C^c \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \left\langle [\max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}), \max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+})], \min(\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c) \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $A^c \vee_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = C^c$.

Hence, $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = A^c \vee_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = C^c$.

Proposition 3.11 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in EC_{m \times n}^P$. Then

- (i) $A^c \wedge_P A^c = A^c$.
- (ii) $A^c \wedge_P B^c = A^c$.
- (iii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = A^c \wedge_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = A^c$.

Proof. Let $A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^c = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^P$.

Then (i) $A^c \wedge_P A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_P A^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \lambda_{ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \wedge_P A^c &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^c \wedge_P B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \wedge_P B^c &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P C^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P C^c \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_P C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle}) \wedge_P C^{\langle} &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $A^{\langle} \wedge_P (B^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}$.

Hence, $(A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle}) \wedge_P C^{\langle} = A^{\langle} \wedge_P (B^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}$.

Proposition 3.12 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}, C^{\langle} \in EC_{m \times n}^R$. Then

(i) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} = A^{\langle}$.

(ii) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} = A^{\langle}$.

(iii) $(A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R C^{\langle} = A^{\langle} \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}$.

Proof. Let $A^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^R$.

Then (i) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R A^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \lambda_{ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle$ for all i, j .

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R C^{\langle} = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R C^{\langle}$.

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R C^{\langle} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R C^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R C^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R C^{\langle} &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $A^{\langle} \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}$.

Hence, $(A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R C^{\langle} = A^{\langle} \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}$.

Theorem 3.13 Let $A_1^{\langle}, A_2^{\langle}, A_3^{\langle}, \dots, A_k^{\langle} \in EC_{m \times n}^P$. Since $A_1^{\langle} \subseteq_P A_2^{\langle} \subseteq_P A_3^{\langle} \subseteq_P \dots \subseteq_P A_k^{\langle}$.

Then $A_1^{\langle} \vee_P A_2^{\langle} \vee_P A_3^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} = A_k^{\langle}$.

Proof. Let

$$A_1^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle, A_2^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \right\rangle, A_3^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle, \dots,$$

$$A_k^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^P.$$

Then, $A_1^{\langle} \vee_P A_2^{\langle} \vee_P A_3^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} = (A_1^{\langle} \vee_P A_2^{\langle}) \vee_P A_3^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle}$.

Since, $A_1^{\langle} \subseteq_P A_2^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \leq \lambda_{2ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{2ij}^a\} \right\rangle \vee_P A_3^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P A_3^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P A_4^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Since, $A_2^{\langle} \subseteq_P A_3^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{3ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{2ij}^a \leq \lambda_{3ij}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{2ij}^a, \lambda_{3ij}^a\} \right\rangle \vee_P A_4^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P A_4^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{4ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P A_5^{\langle} \vee_P \dots \vee_P A_k^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Continuing the same process we get,

$$= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle.$$

Since, $A_{(k-1)}^{\langle} \subseteq_P A_k^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{kij}^a$ and $\lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a \leq \lambda_{kij}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a, \lambda_{kij}^a\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{kij}^a, \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A_k^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.14 Let $A_1^{(c)}, A_2^{(c)}, A_3^{(c)}, \dots, A_k^{(c)} \in ECISM_{m \times n}^R$. Since $A_1^{(c)} \subseteq_R A_2^{(c)} \subseteq_R A_3^{(c)} \subseteq_R \dots \subseteq_R A_k^{(c)}$.

Then $A_1^{(c)} \vee_R A_2^{(c)} \vee_R A_3^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} = A_k^{(c)}$.

Proof. Let

$$A_1^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \rangle, A_2^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \rangle, A_3^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \rangle, \dots,$$

$$A_k^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \rangle \in ECISM_{m \times n}^R.$$

Then, $A_1^{(c)} \vee_R A_2^{(c)} \vee_R A_3^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} = (A_1^{(c)} \vee_R A_2^{(c)}) \vee_R A_3^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)}$.

Since, $A_1^{(c)} \subseteq_R A_2^{(c)} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \geq \lambda_{2ij}^a$ for all i, j.

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{2ij}^a\} \rangle \right) \vee_R A_3^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} \text{ for all i, j} \\ &= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \rangle \right) \vee_R A_3^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} \\ &= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \rangle \right) \vee_R A_4^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

Since, $A_2^{(c)} \subseteq_R A_3^{(c)} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{3ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{2ij}^a \geq \lambda_{3ij}^a$ for all i, j.

Again by Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{2ij}^a, \lambda_{3ij}^a\} \rangle \right) \vee_R A_4^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} \text{ for all i, j} \\ &= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \rangle \right) \vee_R A_4^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)} \\ &= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle [\tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{4ij}^a \rangle \right) \vee_R A_5^{(c)} \vee_R \dots \vee_R A_k^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

Continuing the same process we get,

$$= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \rangle \right).$$

Since, $A_{(k-1)}^{(c)} \subseteq_R A_k^{(c)} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{kij}^a$ and $\lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a \geq \lambda_{kij}^a$ for all i, j.

Again by Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{(k-1)ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{(k-1)ij}^a, \lambda_{kij}^a\} \rangle \right) \text{ for all i, j} \\ &= \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \rangle \right) \\ &= \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{kij}^a, \lambda_{kij}^a \rangle \right) \\ &= A_k^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.15 Let $A_1^{(c)}, A_2^{(c)}, A_3^{(c)}, \dots, A_k^{(c)} \in ECISM_{m \times n}^P$. Since $A_1^{(c)} \subseteq_P A_2^{(c)} \subseteq_P A_3^{(c)} \subseteq_P \dots \subseteq_P A_k^{(c)}$.

Then $A_1^{(c)} \wedge_P A_2^{(c)} \wedge_P A_3^{(c)} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(c)} = A_1^{(c)}$.

Proof. Let

$$A_1^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \rangle, A_2^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \rangle, A_3^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \rangle, \dots,$$

$$A_k^{(c)} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \rangle \in ECISM_{m \times n}^P.$$

Then, $A_1^{(c)} \wedge_P A_2^{(c)} \wedge_P A_3^{(c)} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(c)} = (A_1^{(c)} \wedge_P A_2^{(c)}) \wedge_P A_3^{(c)} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(c)}$.

Since, $A_1^{(c)} \subseteq_P A_2^{(c)} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \leq \lambda_{2ij}^a$ for all i, j.

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{2ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_3^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(} \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_3^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(} \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_4^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(}. \end{aligned}$$

Since, $A_1^{(} \subseteq_P A_3^{(} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{3ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \leq \lambda_{3ij}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{3ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_3^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(} \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_4^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(} \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{4ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{4ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P A_5^{(} \wedge_P \dots \wedge_P A_k^{(}. \end{aligned}$$

Continuing the same process we get,

$$= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle \right).$$

Since, $A_1^{(} \subseteq_P A_k^{(} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{kij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \leq \lambda_{kij}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{kij}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \\ &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \\ &= A_1^{(}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.16 Let $A_1^{(}, A_2^{(}, A_3^{(}, \dots, A_k^{(} \in ECISM_{m \times n}^R$. Since $A_1^{(} \subseteq_R A_2^{(} \subseteq_R A_3^{(} \subseteq_R \dots \subseteq_R A_k^{(}$.

Then $A_1^{(} \wedge_R A_2^{(} \wedge_R A_3^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(} = A_1^{(}$.

Proof. Let

$$A_1^{(} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle, A_2^{(} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{2ij}^a \right\rangle, A_3^{(} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle, \dots,$$

$$A_k^{(} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kij}^{a+}], \lambda_{kij}^a \right\rangle \in ECISM_{m \times n}^R.$$

Then, $A_1^{(} \wedge_R A_2^{(} \wedge_R A_3^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(} = (A_1^{(} \wedge_R A_2^{(}) \wedge_R A_3^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(}$.

Since, $A_1^{(} \subseteq_R A_2^{(} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{2ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \geq \lambda_{2ij}^a$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{2ij}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{1ij}^a, \lambda_{2ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_3^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(} \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_3^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(} \\ &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{1ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{3ij}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_4^{(} \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^{(}. \end{aligned}$$

Since, $A_1^{(} \subseteq_R A_3^{(} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{3ij}^a$ and $\lambda_{1ij}^a \geq \lambda_{3ij}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{3j}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{3j}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{1j}^a, \lambda_{3j}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_3^c \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^c \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}], \lambda_{1j}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_4^c \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^c \\
 &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}], \lambda_{1j}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{4j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{4j}^{a+}], \lambda_{4j}^a \right\rangle \right) \wedge_R A_5^c \wedge_R \dots \wedge_R A_k^c .
 \end{aligned}$$

Continuing the same process we get,

$$= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}], \lambda_{1j}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{kj}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kj}^{a+}], \lambda_{kj}^a \right\rangle \right).$$

Since, $A_1^c \subseteq_R A_k^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{1j}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{kj}^a$ and $\lambda_{1j}^a \geq \lambda_{kj}^a$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{kj}^{a-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}, \tilde{A}_{kj}^{a+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{1j}^a, \lambda_{kj}^a\} \right\rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{1j}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{1j}^{a+}], \lambda_{1j}^a \right\rangle \right) \\
 &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{1j}^a, \lambda_{1j}^a \right\rangle \right) \\
 &= A_1^c .
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.17 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$, then

$$(A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = (A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = B^c .$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}^P$.

Then, L.H.S = $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P C^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c &= \left(\left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \wedge_P C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_P C^c \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle .
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_P C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By the Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= B^c .
 \end{aligned}$$

R.H.S = $(A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c)$.

Then, $(A^c \wedge_P C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_P C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p C^c) &= \langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(B^c \wedge_p C^c) = \langle ([\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b) \wedge_p ([\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c) \rangle$.

Since $B^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (B^c \wedge_p C^c) &= \langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ (A^c \wedge_p C^c) \vee_p (B^c \wedge_p C^c) &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_p \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= A^c \vee_p B^c. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p C^c) \vee_p (B^c \wedge_p C^c) &= \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= B^c. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(A^c \vee_p B^c) \wedge_p C^c = (A^c \wedge_p C^c) \vee_p (B^c \wedge_p C^c) = B^c$.

Theorem 3.18 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ECSM_{m \times n}^R$, then

$$(A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = B^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}^R$.

Then, L.H.S = $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = \langle ([\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a) \vee_R ([\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b) \rangle \wedge_R C^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c &= \langle ([\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}) \rangle \wedge_R C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_R C^c \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_R \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= B^c.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c)$$

$$\text{Then, } (A^c \wedge_R C^c) = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle.$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A^c \wedge_R C^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then, } (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle.$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (B^c \wedge_R C^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= A^c \vee_R B^c.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By the Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\
 &= B^c.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Hence, } (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = B^c.$$

Theorem 3.19 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in EC_{m \times n}^P$, then

$$(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = (A^c \vee_P C^c) \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c) = C^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^c = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in IC_{m \times n}^P$.

$$\text{Then, L.H.S} = (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = \left\langle \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right\rangle \vee_P C^c.$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By the Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p B^c) \vee_p C^c &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \vee_p C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p C^c \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = (A^c \vee_p C^c) \wedge_p (B^c \vee_p C^c)$$

$$\text{Then, } (A^c \vee_p C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then, } (B^c \vee_p C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (B^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ (A^c \vee_p C^c) \wedge_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \wedge_p \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c \wedge_p C^c. \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 3.11(i),

$$(A^c \vee_p C^c) \wedge_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) = C^c. \text{ Hence, } (A^c \wedge_p B^c) \vee_p C^c = (A^c \vee_p C^c) \wedge_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) = C^c.$$

Theorem 3.20 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in EC\text{SM}_{m \times n}^R$, then

$$(A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = (A^c \vee_R C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = C^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^c = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC\text{SM}_{m \times n}^R$.

$$\text{Then, L.H.S} = (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right) \vee_R C^c.$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \vee_R C^{\langle} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right) \vee_R C^{\langle} \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R C^{\langle} \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}).$$

$$\text{Then, } (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then, } (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $B^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \\ (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 3.12(i), $(A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = C^{\langle}$.

Hence, $(A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle}) \vee_R C^{\langle} = (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) \wedge_R (B^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = C^{\langle}$.

Theorem 3.21 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}, C^{\langle} \in EC_{m \times n}^P$, then

$$A^{\langle} \vee_P (B^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = (A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle}) \wedge_P (A^{\langle} \vee_P C^{\langle}) = B^{\langle}.$$

Proof. Let $A^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^P$.

$$\text{Then, L.H.S} = A^{\langle} \vee_P (B^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle} \vee_P \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \vee_p (B^c \wedge_p C^c) &= A^c \vee_p \left(\left\langle [\min(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}), \min(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+})], \min(\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c) \right\rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= B^c. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = (A^c \vee_p B^c) \wedge_p (A^c \vee_p C^c).$$

$$\text{Then, } (A^c \vee_p B^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_p B^c) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Then, } (A^c \vee_p C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right).$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ (A^c \vee_p B^c) \wedge_p (A^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_p \left\langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= B^c \wedge_p C^c. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle}) \wedge_P (A^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= B^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $A^{\langle} \vee_P (B^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = (A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle}) \wedge_P (A^{\langle} \vee_P C^{\langle}) = B^{\langle}$.

Theorem 3.22 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}, C^{\langle} \in EC_{m \times n}^R$, then

$$A^{\langle} \vee_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = (A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = B^{\langle}.$$

Proof. Let $A^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^{\langle} = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^R$.

Then, L.H.S = $A^{\langle} \vee_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle} \vee_R \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $B^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \vee_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) &= A^{\langle} \vee_R \left(\left\langle [\min(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}), \min(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+})], \max(\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c) \right\rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^{\langle} \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= B^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

R.H.S = $(A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle})$.

Then, $(A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) &= \left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) &= \langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \\ &= \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \\ (A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R (A^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) &= \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \\ &= B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^{\langle} \subseteq_R C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R (A^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) &= \langle [\min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \\ &= B^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $A^{\langle} \vee_R (B^{\langle} \wedge_R C^{\langle}) = (A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle}) \wedge_R (A^{\langle} \vee_R C^{\langle}) = B^{\langle}$.

Theorem 3.23 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}, C^{\langle} \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$, then

$$A^{\langle} \wedge_P (B^{\langle} \vee_P C^{\langle}) = (A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle}) \vee_P (A^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle}.$$

Proof. Let $A^{\langle} = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^{\langle} = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^{\langle} = \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ECSM_{m \times n}^P$.

Then, L.H.S = $A^{\langle} \wedge_P (B^{\langle} \vee_P C^{\langle}) = A^{\langle} \wedge_P \left(\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_P \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$.

Since $B^{\langle} \subseteq_P C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_P (B^{\langle} \vee_P C^{\langle}) &= A^{\langle} \wedge_P \left(\langle [\max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}), \max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+})], \max(\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c) \rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^{\langle} \wedge_P \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \\ &= \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_P C^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

R.H.S = $(A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle}) \vee_P (A^{\langle} \wedge_P C^{\langle})$.

Then, $(A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle}) = \left(\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right)$.

Since $A^{\langle} \subseteq_P B^{\langle} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p B^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(A^c \wedge_p C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_p \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_p C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p C^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ (A^c \wedge_p B^c) \vee_p (A^c \vee_p C^c) &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_p \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c \vee_p A^c. \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 3.9(i), $(A^c \wedge_p C^c) \vee_p (B^c \wedge_p C^c) = A^c$.

Hence, $A^c \wedge_p (B^c \vee_p C^c) = (A^c \wedge_p B^c) \vee_p (A^c \wedge_p C^c) = A^c$.

Theorem 3.24 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in EC_{m \times n}^R$, then

$$A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_R C^c) = A^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle, B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle, C^c = \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \in EC_{m \times n}^R$.

Then, L.H.S = $A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = A^c \wedge_R \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $B^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{B}_{ij}^b \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\mu_{ij}^b \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) &= A^c \wedge_R \left(\left\langle [\max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}), \max(\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+})], \min(\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c) \right\rangle \right) \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c. \end{aligned}$$

R.H.S = $(A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_R C^c)$.

Then, $(A^c \wedge_R B^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_R B^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $(A^c \wedge_R C^c) = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \right)$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_R C^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{C}_{ij}^c$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \gamma_{ij}^c$ for all i, j .

Again by Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_R C^c) &= \left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \right\rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \vee_R C^c) &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^c \vee_R A^c. \end{aligned}$$

By Proposition 3.10(i), $(A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = A^c$.

Hence, $A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_R C^c) = A^c$.

Theorem 3.25 Let $A^c, B^c \in EC_{m \times n}^P$. Then

(i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c)^c = B^c \wedge_P A^c$.

(ii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c)^c = B^c \vee_P A^c$.

Proof. Let $A^c = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle$ and $B^c = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle$.

(i) L.H.S = $(A^c \vee_P B^c)^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c$.

Since $A^c \subseteq_P B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right)^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, 1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], 1 - \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}, 1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}], 1 - \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

R.H.S = $B^c \wedge_P A^c$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c \wedge_P \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^c \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle.$$

Since $B^{(c)} \subseteq_P A^{(c)}$, by Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\min\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}, \min\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}], \min\{1 - \mu_{ij}^b, 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

L.H.S = R.H.S

So $(A^{(c)} \vee_P B^{(c)})^c = B^{(c)} \wedge_P A^{(c)}$.

$$(ii) \quad \text{L.H.S} = (A^{(c)} \wedge_P B^{(c)})^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c.$$

Since $A^{(c)} \subseteq_P B^{(c)} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \leq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.5(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right)^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, 1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], 1 - \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}, 1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}], 1 - \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = B^{(c)} \vee_P A^{(c)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c \vee_P \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^c \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^{(c)} \subseteq_P A^{(c)}$, by Definition 3.5(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\max\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}, \max\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}], \max\{1 - \mu_{ij}^b, 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^{(c)}. \end{aligned}$$

L.H.S = R.H.S

So $(A^{(c)} \wedge_P B^{(c)})^c = B^{(c)} \vee_P A^{(c)}$.

Theorem 3.26 Let $A^{(c)}, B^{(c)} \in ECSM_{m \times n}^R$. Then

$$(i) \quad (A^{(c)} \vee_R B^{(c)})^c = B^{(c)} \wedge_R A^{(c)}.$$

$$(ii) \quad (A^{(c)} \wedge_R B^{(c)})^c = B^{(c)} \vee_R A^{(c)}.$$

Proof. Let $A^{(c)} = \left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle$ and $B^{(c)} = \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle$.

$$(i) \quad \text{L.H.S} = (A^c \vee_R B^c)^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c.$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right)^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, 1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], 1 - \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}, 1 - \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}], 1 - \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle. \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = B^{c^c} \wedge_R A^{c^c}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c \wedge_R \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^c \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^{c^c} \subseteq_R A^{c^c}$, by Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle [\min\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}\}, \min\{1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}\}], \max\{1 - \mu_{ij}^b, 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

L.H.S = R.H.S

So $(A^c \vee_R B^c)^c = B^{c^c} \wedge_R A^{c^c}$.

$$(ii) \quad \text{L.H.S} = (A^c \wedge_R B^c)^c = \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c.$$

Since $A^c \subseteq_R B^c \Leftrightarrow \tilde{A}_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{B}_{ij}^b$ and $\lambda_{ij}^a \geq \mu_{ij}^b$ for all i, j .

By Definition 3.7(b),

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\left\langle [\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \right)^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}, 1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}], 1 - \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}\}, 1 - \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}\}], 1 - \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\ &= C^c. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{R.H.S} = B^{c^c} \vee_R A^{c^c}$$

$$= \left(\left\langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \right)^c \vee_R \left(\left\langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^c$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle [1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}], 1 - \mu_{ij}^b \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle [1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}], 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $B^{(c)} \subseteq_R A^{(c)}$, by Definition 3.7(a),

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left\langle [\max(1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}), \max(1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, 1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-})], \min(1 - \mu_{ij}^b, 1 - \lambda_{ij}^a) \right\rangle \\
 &= \left\langle [\tilde{C}_{ij}^{c+}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^{c-}], \gamma_{ij}^c \right\rangle \\
 &= C^{(c)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

L.H.S = R.H.S

So $(A^{(c)} \wedge_R B^{(c)})^c = B^{(c)} \vee_R A^{(c)}$.

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